

Next generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials

Catalyst, MPL and MEA specifications and requirements (D3.1)

31 March, 2020

www.newely.eu

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No **875118**. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research.

FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN
JOINT UNDERTAKING

Technical References

Version:	01b	Date:	03.07.2020
Project Title:	Next Generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials		
Acronym:	NEWELY	Contract N°:	875118
Topic:	FCH-02-4-2019	Project Coordinator:	DLR, Germany
Document Classification: ¹	PU - NEWELY public		
Copyright:	This document has been produced and funded under NEWELY Grant Agreement 875118. It is shared with licensing conditions Creative Commons-ShareAlike (CC BYSA): Anybody may remix, tweak, and build upon this work even for commercial purposes, as long as credit is made to the QualyGridS consortium and this document is cited as a source and anybody may license their new creations under the identical terms		
Author (Partner):	Jaromír Hnát (UCTP)	Approved (Coordinator):	03.07.20
Other Authors:	Miriam Goll (CENmat) Schwan Hossein (CENmat) Ansar, Syed Asif (DLR) Fatemeh Sanaz Razmjooei (DLR) Corinna Harms (DLR) Lukas Mues (DLR) Frederik Fouda-Onana (CEA) Karel Bouzek (UCTP)	Released (Coordinator):	03.07.20
Approved (Partner)		Date of first issue:	17.02.20
Distribution:	All NEWELY Partners		

Versions

Version 01 31.03.2020 Finalized document

Version 01b 03.07.2020 Acknowledgement changed, new project logo and layout

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services).

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services).

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

Table of Content

1	Summary	6
2	Introduction	7
3	Catalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction	9
3.1	Pnictidic compounds.....	10
3.2	Chalcogenidic compounds	11
3.3	Metal complexes.....	11
3.4	Carbides	11
4	Catalysts for oxygen evolution reaction	14
5	Benchmark catalysts.....	17
6	Liquid/Gas diffusion layer (LGDL) and Microporous layer (MPL).....	18
7	Membrane electrode assembly	20
7.1	CCM vs. CCS	20
7.2	Electrode preparation	21
7.3	Solution in NEWELY.....	22
7.4	MEA requirements and targets in NEWELY.....	22
8	Conclusion	25
9	Literature.....	26

List of Tables

Table 1 Summary of non-PGM catalysts tested for HER	12
Table 2 Cathode catalyst properties	13
Table 3 Summary of non-PGM catalysts tested for OER, adopted from	15
Table 4 Anode catalyst properties	16
Table 5 Properties and required values for MPLs	19
Table 6 Main specifications of the components comprising an AEM WE	24

List of Figures

Figure 1 Volcano plot of the materials for HER	9
Figure 2 Simplified reaction scheme of the hydrogen evolution reaction mechanism.....	10
Figure 3 Theoretical overpotential for oxygen evolution vs. the difference between the standard free energy of two subsequent intermediates ($\Delta G_{O^*}^0 - \Delta G_{HO}^0$) for various binary oxides.....	14
Figure 4 A) Linear Sweep voltammetry of CENmat's Mo ₂ C coated on carbon felt, compared to Sigma Aldrich Mo ₂ C on carbon felt and pristine carbon felt in 0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄ . B) Polarization curve of a 4 cm ² cell in 0.1 M KOH with CENmat's Ni-Fe-Oxide or Ir-black as anode catalyst.	17

Abbreviations and Indices

Abbreviation	Explanation
AEM	Anion exchange membrane
AEM WE	Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis
CAPEX	Capital expenses
CCM	Catalyst coated membrane
CCS	Catalyst coated substrate
GDL	Gas diffusion layer
HER	Hydrogen evolution reaction
j_0	Exchange current density ($A\ cm^{-2}$)
KOH	Potassium hydroxide
LGDL	Liquid/gas diffusion layer
MEA	Membrane electrode assembly
MPL	Microporous layer
NaOH	Sodium hydroxide
OER	Oxygen evolution reaction
PEMWE	Proton exchange membrane water electrolysis
PGM	Platinum group metals
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
η	Overpotential (V)

1 Summary

This report gives a summarizing overview of state-of-the-art specifications of catalysts, MPL and MEA for AEMWE, outlines the development paths within NEWELY and gives target values for these materials.

2 Introduction

An overpotential (η) represents a driving force of any electrochemical reaction. It is defined as difference between the real electrode potential and its reversible value. The value of the η is directly related to the electrode reaction rate, unless the rate determining step is different from the charge transfer kinetics. The value of η needed to achieve the desired reaction rate can be decreased utilizing the appropriate catalysts. Therefore, significant attention is paid to the development of such materials. General demands on the catalyst are quite clear; they may be summarised as follows [1]:

- Easy to produce
- Cheap
- Electronically conductive
- Active towards the desired electrochemical reaction
- Stable under the conditions of the desired electrochemical reaction
- Environmentally friendly

Only a limited number of materials can meet all these requirements. From the practical point of view, mainly the electrocatalytic activity, long-term stability and cost are thus considered. In proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE) the choice of the materials available for anode and cathode catalyst is strongly limited to the rare metals of the Pt-group, particularly IrO₂ and Pt respectively. In alkaline environment, the range of the promising materials is significantly broader. However, negative consequence of this situation is that no material established up to now as a generally accepted optimal choice. No material is thus available commercially as an anode or cathode catalysts for alkaline water electrolysis. Typically, the catalysts for alkaline environment are based on transition metal (e.g. Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Mo, Ru, Ag, W) and non-metallic element (e.g. B, C, N, O, P, S) [2]. Most of the catalysts reported in the literature so far were tested for application in an alkaline environment represented by 0.1 or 1 mol dm⁻³ sodium or potassium hydroxide (NaOH, or KOH respectively) solution. The aim of the NEWELY project is, however, to operate electrolyzer close to or at neutral pH. This ambitious goal limits the choice of the catalyst materials significantly. Metals like Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu in various chemical forms, however, still represent a viable alternative [3].

Despite the wide range of the alternative materials available for alkaline environment, the utilization of Pt-group metals is not rare in alkaline water electrolysis [4-7]. It is due to their sufficient activity and stability. Pt/C on cathode and IrO₂ on anode side can thus be considered as state-of-the-art Pt group catalysts for water electrolysis generally. However, activity of Pt catalysts towards HER is pH dependent showing continuous decrease in activity with increasing pH of environment [8]. The reason for this is not completely clear for now, but it was shown that in alkaline environment the activity of Pt catalyst can decrease down to half of the value found for the acidic one affecting the parameters like exchange current density (j_0) or Tafel slope [9, 10].

Tafel analysis represents a common approach to the evaluation of the catalyst activity. It is based on plotting of the linear sweep voltammetry polarisation curve (dependence of the current flowing between working and counter electrode on the potential of the working electrode) in the form of the dependence of the overpotential applied to the working electrode on the log of the current density. The Tafel equation is defined by eq. (1).

$$\eta = a + b \log(j) \quad (1)$$

Where

$$a = \frac{2.303RT}{n\alpha F} \log(j_0)$$

$$b = \frac{-2.303RT}{n\alpha F}$$

From the equation above it is clear, that Tafel intercept “a” value is determined primarily by the exchange current density j_0 . As such, it is directly related to the electrode reaction kinetics and thus to the catalyst activity. Constant “b” stands for Tafel slope. Here the only kinetic parameter represents the charge transfer coefficient. Value of j_0 is often evaluated with significant error. Therefore, not all of the authors use this characteristic. Tafel slope generally refers to reaction mechanism, particularly to the rate determining step in the complex reaction mechanism. The unit of the Tafel slope is $V \text{ dec}^{-1}$, which refers to the amount of overpotential necessary for current increase in order of magnitude. This value is generally evaluated by the authors and published in literature for newly developed catalysts [11]. From this reason the value of Tafel slope is used as comparative parameter of different catalyst materials also in this report.

3 Catalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction

The basic overview of the materials appropriate for HER can be summarized in the form of the Sabatiers Volcano plot (see Figure 1). Following the Volcano plot, the highest activity towards HER, show Pt and Pt-group metals (PGM). This is due to the optimal strength of the M-H bond, where M stays for the metal catalyst and H for hydrogen. On the ascending part of the plot, metals like Zn, Cu, Ni, Co etc. can be found. These materials show weaker strength of the M-H bond, making thus desorption of H₂ easier. However, sorption of the reactant to the surface of the catalyst is in this case slower, representing thus the rate determine step. On the other hand, when the M-H bond is too strong, desorption of the H₂ determines the reaction kinetics.

Figure 1 Volcano plot of the materials for HER [12].

The simplified reaction scheme of the hydrogen evolution reaction mechanism in acidic environment is shown in Figure 2. Generally, two different mechanisms (Heyrovsky and Tafel) are considered to be involved in HER. Both mechanisms start with adsorption of reactant (H⁺ or H₂O) on the catalyst surface. It is called Volmer step. Subsequently, adsorbed reactant reacts chemically with another adsorbed reactant (Tafel step) or it reacts directly with the H⁺ ion from solution (Heyrovsky step). The H₂ molecule is released in the next step and active site is cleared.

The mechanism shown in Figure 2 is valid for acidic environment, where H⁺ ions are abundant. However, in neutral or near-neutral the first step of the mechanism is represented by the formation of hydronium and hydroxyl ions, which are in equilibrium with water (eq. (2)).

This step is slow and needs additional energy, mostly supplied in the form of overpotential [3].

Figure 2 Simplified reaction scheme of the hydrogen evolution reaction mechanism.

As stated before, Pt represents the state-of-the-art catalyst for HER. However, many promising materials can be synthesized for neutral → alkaline environment. These materials are often based on 3d-transition metal compounds like pnictides, chalcogenides, borates and borides or metal complexes [3]. It is not possible to clearly distinguish one compound over performing the others. For example, phosphide compounds can show Tafel slopes as low as 63 mV dec^{-1} [13] and as high as 182 mV dec^{-1} [14]. Obviously, the performance of the catalyst is not only dependent on its nature, but it depends also on the composition, morphology, way of the preparation and other parameters. One of the lowest value of the Tafel slope (38 mV dec^{-1}) for HER in neutral solution of pH 7 was achieved by Liu et al. [15].

3.1 Pnictidic compounds

Pnictides represent the elements of the 15th group of the periodic table. Main representatives of pnictides as catalysts for HER are nitrides and phosphides, as arsenides and antimonides are toxic. Promising properties of nitrides and phosphides materials, for HER, are due to their negative polarisation, leading to the attraction of the protons due to the opposite charge [3]. For example, in the case of CoP nanowire array on carbon cloth electrode, high HER activity was observed for the pH of 1, 7 and 14 [16]. Comparison of the activity was made based on the Tafel slopes which achieved values of 51, 93 and 129 mV dec^{-1} for pH 1, 7 and 14 respectively [16]. Apart from Co, Nickel Azides (NiN_x) [17] and Iron Phosphides (Fe_xP) [18] were also used as representatives of 3d transition metal group as promising pnictidic catalysts for neutral water electrolysis.

3.2 Chalcogenidic compounds

Chalcogenides are members of the 16th group of the periodic table (oxygen group). Generally, metal chalcogenides show high activity towards HER and sufficient stability in entire pH range [19]. However, they undergo significant changes when exposed to the conditions of the OER in neutral or alkaline solutions [20]. The most commonly used chalcogenide for catalyst designed for neutral or near-neutral water electrolysis is the sulphur (S) [19, 21, 22]. Nevertheless, selenium (Se) is mentioned in the literature as well [23]. For example, Tafel slopes measured by Zheng et al. at pH 1, 7 and 14 were 44, 68 and 118 mV dec⁻¹ respectively [24].

3.3 Metal complexes

Complexes of many of the 3d-transition metals are prone to hydrolysis when exposed to water. The hydrolysis is faster the more pH differs from the neutral value. In order to prevent spontaneous hydrolysis of the catalyst, the metal particle is protected by bulky hydrophobic ligands. This approach protects the metal atom in the centre of the catalyst molecule. On the other hand, it decreases activity of the catalyst inevitable. It is simply due to the fact, that the number of water molecules reaching the catalytic metal centre to be split is limited [3]. Mainly the Co is used a central atom of this catalyst [25, 26]. Nevertheless, copper (Cu) can be used as well [27].

3.4 Carbides

Metal carbides represent another promising solution for HER in nearly neutral or neutral environment [28]. Similarly to phosphide and nitrides, DFT calculation shows, that even carbides has nearly the same d-band electronic density as noble metals [28]. Even more, the structural flexibility of carbides allows the compatibility with conductive materials like carbon, graphene and others. Especially tungsten carbide seems to be perspective material for HER due to their Pt-like properties. Despite the fact of the achieved promising results in terms of activity, it is still necessary to conduct structural optimization of these materials in order to achieve high HER activity necessary to fulfil the aims of the NEWELY project.

Table 1 provides overview of the of the activity parameter of the different classes of the catalysts for HER. As indicators of the catalytic activity the overpotential at current density - 10 mA cm⁻² and value of the Tafel slope are used. Besides the activity parameters the Table contains additional information on the pH of the catalyst working environment and, if available, Faradic yield. This value corresponds to the part of electric charge passed used for HER. Value lower than 100 % thus indicates side reactions occurrence, which is in this system commonly connected with the catalyst changes/degradation.

Table 1 Summary of non-PGM catalysts tested for HER, adopted from [50]

Catalyst material	η @ -10 mA cm ⁻² mV	Tafel slope (mV per decade)	pH	Faradaic yield	Refs
CoMo	170 (100 mA cm ⁻²)	92	14.8	NA	[29]
NiMo	200 (100 mA cm ⁻²)	122	14.8	NA	[29]
NiMo	34 (20 mA cm ⁻²)	NA	14	NA	[30]
MoS ₂	~150	41	0	NA	[31]
CoS ₂	145	51	0	NA	[32]
CoMoS _x	250	85	7	100% [§]	[33]
WS ₂	~250	60	0	NA	[34]
CoSe ₂	90	39	0	NA	[35]
MoSSe	~200	56	0	100%*	[36]
NiSe ₂	~140	49	0	NA	[37]
Ni ₂ P	130 (20 mA cm ⁻²)	46	0	100%*	[38]
CoP	85 (20 mA cm ⁻²)	50	0	100%*	[39]
FeP	55	38	0	100% [§]	[40]
MoP S	64	NA	0	100% [§]	[41]
CoN _x	170	75	14	NA	[42]
CoN _x	140	30	0	NA	[42]
NiMoN _x	225 (5 mA cm ⁻²)	36	1	NA	[43]
Co _{0.6} Mo _{1.4} N ₂	200	NA	1	>90%*	[44]
α -MoB	~225 (20 mA cm ⁻²)	55	-0.3	100% [†]	[45]
Mo ₂ C	130	53	0	NA	[46]

MoC	124	43	0	NA	[47]
MoC	77	50	14	NA	[47]
Ni/C	34	41	0	100%*	[48]
Cu ₉₅ Ti ₅	60	110	13	NA	[49]

NA, no analysis. *Quantified by measuring volume of gases evolved. ‡ Quantified by gas chromatography. § Quantification method not stated

From Table 1 follows that carbides belong among the clearly promising materials. They show remarkable performance at pH values as low as 0 and high as 14. The Tafel slopes show under both pH conditions low values of about 50 mV dec⁻¹ and promising overpotential at 10 mA cm⁻² with values as low as 77 mV [47]. This group of materials thus show high potential for further development within the NEWELY project.

In Table 2 the properties of the desired catalyst for the cathode in the NEWELY project are summarized.

Table 2 Cathode catalyst properties

Property, Unit	Required Value
Synthesis technique	Preferably wet chemical route, preferably at ambient pressure
chemical precursors	No critical raw materials, preferably no toxic chemicals
Total weight of synthesized catalyst, g	Minimum 3 g per batch
particle size, nm	<30 (some agglomerates)
min BET surface area, m² g⁻¹	80
Cost, EUR g⁻¹	TBD, based on commercial precursors purchased in small amounts
max. Tafel slope, mV dec⁻¹	85
max. overpotential, mV @ 1 mA cm⁻², pH 7¹	15

¹Target Milestone M3.1: Nanostructured OER and HER catalyst reach overpotentials of 15 mV @ 1 mA cm⁻² vs. RHE in half-cell measurements in pH 7.

4 Catalysts for oxygen evolution reaction

Similarly, to the HER catalysts, volcano plot of the promising materials in the form of the oxides for OER is shown in Figure 3. An ideal catalyst for OER should be able to operate i) in wide pH range, ii) at low overpotentials with high current densities, iii) for extended period of time (from years to decade). Concerning the composition and production of the ideal OER material, it should consist from earth-abundant materials via a simple and economical method. First-row transition metal compounds such as Co-, Ni-, and Fe-based materials have been extensively investigated as efficient electrocatalysts for overall water splitting [51]. Their excellent OER activity is due to their multivalent oxidation states ($M^{+2/+3/+4}$), which are proved to be the active sites for OER. Furthermore, their OER activities are highly dependent on the morphology, composition, oxidation state, their electronic structure, the surface oxygen binding energy and the enthalpy for the lower to higher oxide transition [52]. Different compounds of the mentioned transition metals can be used for OER in neutral \rightarrow alkaline solutions. These are oxides [53], hydroxides [54], layered double hydroxides [55], sulphides [56], borates [57] or carbonates [58].

Figure 3 Theoretical overpotential for oxygen evolution vs. the difference between the standard free energy of two subsequent intermediates ($\Delta G_{O^*}^0 - \Delta G_{HO^*}^0$) for various binary oxides [59].

Figure 3 depicts the theoretical overpotential for OER for various binary oxides. It can be seen that one of the most active catalyst for OER is ruthenium dioxide (RuO_2). However, RuO_2 shows only limited stability under OER conditions, especially at higher overpotentials [60]. Superior durability offers IrO_2 , just below RuO_2 in the Volcano plot due to which it is dealt as state-of-the-art OER catalyst in the current PEM water electrolysis operating with neutral water environment. Yet, its limited abundance and high costs are responsible for the high capital expenses (CAPEX) of the today's PEM water electrolyzers.

However, in alkaline solutions, the spectrum of the possible OER catalysts expands also to non-Pt metals such as Co [53], Ni [23], Mn [61], or Fe [62]. For OER catalysts consisting of these metals a wide range of Tafel slopes can be found in scientific literature ranging from 36 mV dec^{-1} [63] to 370 mV dec^{-1} [54]. Interestingly, many of the materials showing Tafel slopes below 100 mV dec^{-1} utilized Co as 3d transition metal cation [64-66]. The overview of the promising materials is shown in Table 3. It utilizes, again, the values of overpotential and Tafel slope. However, due to the abundance in literature, the overpotential at current density of 1 mA cm^{-2} is used in this case.

Table 3 Summary of non-PGM catalysts tested for OER, adopted from [50]

Catalyst material	$\eta @ 1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ (mV)	Tafel slope (mV per decade)	pH	Faradaic yield	Refs
Fe film	540	47	7	NA	[62]
NiFe oxides	30	15	14	NA	[67]
NiFe oxides	~120	32	15	NA	[68]
NiFe oxides	210	31	14	~100%*	[69]
NiCo oxides	370	NA	13	NA	[70]
NiMo oxides	300	47	14	NA	[71]
FeCoW oxy-hydroxides	191 (10 mAcm^{-2})	NA	14	100%*	[72]
$\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$	~320	~60	13	NA	[73]
NiCoCe oxides	250	~60	14	97%*	[74]
$\alpha\text{-Fe}_{33}\text{Co}_{33}\text{Ni}_{33}\text{O}_x$	230	30	13	NA	[75]
Co oxides	410	60	7	100% [‡]	[76]
Co oxides	390	60	9.2	100% [‡]	[77]
Co_3O_4	300	49	14	NA	[78]
Co oxides	~480	~120	3.5	>95% [‡]	[79]
CoP	345 (10 mAcm^{-2})	47	14	100%*	[80]

CoMnP	330 (10 mAcm ⁻²)	61	14	96%*	[81]
Ni oxides	380	30	9.2	100% ‡	[82]
Ni oxides	320 (10 mAcm ⁻²)	52	14	~100%*	[83]
Mn oxides	280	NA	14	NA	[84]

NA, no analysis. *Quantified by measuring volume of gases evolved. ‡ Quantified by gas chromatography. § Quantification method not stated

Based on the values in Table 3 it is possible to see that NiFe catalysts show both the low Tafel slope as well as overpotential at 1 mA cm⁻². This was achieved at high pH of 14, but the application of the Fe based catalyst was reported even for neutral environment of pH 7 [62]. In the case of a neutral environment Tafel slope value was as low as 47 mV dec⁻¹ [62]. The overpotential at 1 mA cm⁻² achieved promising value of 540 mV [62]. This value is higher than expected by NEWELY project, but the space for improvement is still available. Even more, NiFe based catalysts don't contain any strategic raw element, which give them high chance for industrial application. Therefore, NEWELY project will focus in the field of OER catalyst on the materials based on the NiFe compounds or alloys.

Table 4 summarizes the properties of the desired catalyst for the anode in the NEWELY project.

Table 4 Anode catalyst properties

Property, Unit	Required Value
Synthesis technique	Preferably wet chemical route, preferably at ambient pressure
Chemical precursors	No critical raw materials, preferably no toxic chemicals
Total weight of synthesized catalyst, g	Minimum 3 g per batch
particle size, nm	<60 (some agglomerates)
min BET surface area, m² g⁻¹	75
Cost, EUR g⁻¹	TBD, based on commercial precursors purchased in small amounts
max. Tafel slope, mV dec⁻¹	45
max. overpotential, mV @ 1 mA cm⁻², pH 7¹	400

¹Target Milestone M3.1: Nanostructured OER and HER catalyst reach overpotentials of 400 mV @ 1 mA cm⁻² vs. RHE in half-cell measurements in pH 7.

5 Benchmark catalysts

As benchmark HER catalyst molybdenum carbide (Mo_2C) from CENmat was chosen. Mo_2C exhibits a wide abundance, low cost and a similar d-orbital electronic structure compared to the PGM-catalyst platinum, which makes it a favourable non-PGM benchmark [85]. It exhibits a very good performance with an overpotential of 50 mV @ -10 mA cm^{-2} at pH 0. It is to our knowledge the only commercially available PGM-free catalyst designed especially for the application in the anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. Figure 4A shows its polarization curve compared to Mo_2C purchased from Aldrich which is clearly proving its feasibility as HER catalyst.

As benchmark OER catalyst Nickel-Iron-Oxide ($\text{Ni}_x\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_z$) from CENmat was chosen, as mixed transition metal oxides are with their high abundance and low cost and their high activity and stability most suited candidates for OER catalysis in alkaline media. Nickel-Iron-Oxide from CENmat exhibits excellent activity and stability at moderate pH. With an overpotential of 260 mV @ 10 mA cm^{-2} at pH 13 this catalyst shows an activity close to the PGM-benchmark Iridium-Black. Figure 4B shows the only minor difference of the polarization behaviour of a 4 cm^2 cell in 0.1 M KOH, anode loaded with CENmat's Ni-Fe-Oxide or Ir-black respectively.

Figure 4 A) Linear Sweep voltammetry of CENmat's Mo_2C coated on carbon felt, compared to Sigma Aldrich Mo_2C on carbon felt and pristine carbon felt in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 . B) Polarization curve of a 4 cm^2 cell in 0.1 M KOH with CENmat's Ni-Fe-Oxide or Ir-black as anode catalyst.

6 Liquid/Gas diffusion layer (LGDL) and Microporous layer (MPL)

A liquid/gas diffusion layer (LGDL) is placed between the bipolar plate (BP) and membrane electrode assembly (MEA). LGDL is generally composed of a bilayer structure comprising a macro-porous backing material and a micro-porous layer (MPL) on top. The LGDLs with versatile roles are expected to transport electrons, heat, and reactants/products (H_2O , OH^- , O_2 , and H_2) to and from the active sites of catalyst layer with minimum voltage, current, thermal, interfacial and fluidic losses. This is necessary for improving efficiency and performance of electrolyzers. Therefore, the performance of electrolyzer highly depends on the properties of LGDL. Material with desirable properties for use as the multifunctional LGDLs should show high durability specifically in highly corrosive condition in neutral to alkaline environment of AEMWE. One of such materials with high chemical stability for use as the LGDL as the anode side of a PEMWE is titanium (Ti) [86-88]. Therefore, nowadays, Ti is mainly used as the construction material of an anode gas diffusion layer in the form of woven mesh, metallic foams, and sintered fibre felt in PEMWE. However, Ti is still expensive and not appealing for commercial application. AEMWE operated in pure water has the potential to become a cheaper alternative to its counterpart PEMWE by allowing for the use of less inexpensive cell components. Vincent et al [89] have listed many cases whereby the anode GDL was made of Ni foam, stainless steel mesh and even Carbon paper. At the cathode side, in most of cases carbon based GDL was used. In many cases [4, 90] Toray GDL was used. Such GDL are known to be without MPL, but the substrate is hydrophobized. In PEMWE, to the best of our knowledge, it was not demonstrated the impact of PTFE treated or the absence of microporous layer (MPL) GDL cathode onto the performance of the water electrolysis cell.

On the other hand, MPLs represent an important element of the LGDL and play an important role in the performance of electrolyzers, reducing contact resistance and improving reactant/product management [86]. Therefore, surface modification by forming MPLs as coating on macro porous stainless steel LGDL with optimal designs of thickness, porosity and pore size/shape can yield low interfacial contact resistance (ICR) between the various cell components. It also allows for of facile mass transport of reactants and products (H_2O , OH^- , O_2 , and H_2) without diffusion limitations. This all leads to a decrease in ohmic resistance. Furthermore, forming microporous layers (MPLs) as coating mitigate the mass transfer issues at high current densities originating from optimal capillary pressure, which in turns can decrease the mass transfer resistance. These all lead to increase the overall performance and efficiency of electrolyzers. Despite the PEMWE, very few attempts have been carried out to produce appropriate MPLs, which are suitable for AEMWE environment. The LGDLs and MPLs, which have rarely been investigated for AEMWE, can be a key factor for managing mass transport in the presence of two-phase flow while providing the mechanical support for membrane-electrode assembly (MEA) and a BP. Usually, Ti and Nb powders are used to fabricate MPLs on the top of LGDLs for PEMWE [86-88]. However; the non-corrosive AEMWE environment using DI water allows using less expensive materials such as Ni based materials to fabricate MPLs on the top of LGDL. In particular, LGDL coated MPLs in AEMWE provides the following [86].

1. Simultaneous liquid/gas permeabilities: distributing liquid water through the cell to access the reaction sites, which improve the catalyst utilization and reduce the activation loss,

providing pathways for oxygen and hydrogen gas removal from the electrodes, which in turns reduce their local concentration to improve the overall performance.

2. Electrical and thermal conductivities: conduct and the same time take away electrons from the reaction sites at the anode and cathode, and maintain a uniform temperature distribution within the cell.

3. Chemical, interfacial and mechanical properties: protecting the stainless steel LGDL against corrosion and lowering interfacial contacts with the neighbouring parts such as BP and membrane electrode assembly (MEA) and also retaining minimum effect on pressure drops.

Several parameters such as porosity pore size distribution, gas permeability, tortuosity and leakage rates need to be optimized in order to ensure an optimum electrical contact to the different cell components to minimise the ohmic, activation and concentration losses consequently improve overall cell performance. The properties and required values for the MPLs are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Properties and required values for MPLs.

Property, Unit	Required Value
Pressure drop, Pa*	0.05 MPa or less
Thickness of MPL	$\cong 80 \mu\text{m}$
Porosity	30-40%
Pore size, μm	1-10 μm , some interlayer pores larger than 10 μm
Contact resistance/ (@ 150-200 N/cm ²)	13-25 m Ω .cm ²
Decrease in cell over-potential	300 mV at 1 A cm ⁻²
Ohmic drop	$\cong 0.4-0.50 \Omega$.cm ⁻²
Roughness factor, μm	TBD for 2layers, 11.5 - 16 (8layers) [87]
Cost , €/m ²	TBD
Gas saturation	TBD
Permeability, mol cm ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ bar ⁻¹	$5.32 \cdot 10^{-11}$ [91]
Tortuosity	TBD for 2layers, 2-5 (8layers) [87]
Bubble point, hPa	2-5
Hydrophobicity, °	TBD
Proposed material(s)	Stainless steel and Nickel based materials

Consequently, in NEWELY, both anode and cathode LGDL/MPⁿ will be Stainless steel and Nickel based materials.

7 Membrane electrode assembly

The MEA represents the main component of the hydrogen electrochemical generator. Based on the development that was done so far in PEM technology for fuel cell or water electrolysis, we can separate the preparation of the MEA for AEMWE into two categories: catalyst coated support type (CCS), where the catalyst layer is coated onto a porous electrically conductive compound or catalyst coated membrane type (CCM). In this section, we will report the best practice in MEA preparation based on a literature survey. Different topics that play an important role for the final performance of the electrochemical reactor will be discussed:

- CCM vs. CCS
- Diffusion Layers
- electrode preparation (catalyst, loading, binder, loading)
- solution feeding

7.1 CCM vs. CCS

The literature survey has shown that most MEAs produced so far were CCS type. Probably it allows a better adhesion of the electrode on the porous compound which contributes to a better durability.

Ito et al. [92] have considered a dual approach whereby the anode part of the MEA was CCS like, while the cathode counterpart was CCM. Since the cell was feed on the anode only (they have found that the water diffusion through the membrane is large enough for the hydrogen evolution reaction) they have coated the IrO₂ electrode on the porous titanium at the anode and the platinum-based cathode on the membrane.

Compared with CCS, the CCM is supposed to reduce the ion transfer resistance between the electrolyte of the membrane and its corresponding part within the electrode. In section 7.2, the influence of binder chemistry and content will be discussed more exhaustively.

Anion exchange membranes have a lower thermal stability than the proton conducting membranes [93]. A CCM production through transfer mechanism above 100°C will severely damage the membrane, thus for CCM MEAs the main strategy is to coat the active ink directly onto the membrane either via spray coating [93] or screen printing [94].

In several publications [4, 5, 95] the spray coating is the most used technique for applying the active layer. The screen printing method that requires more material, might be difficult to apply in the early stage of NEWELY AEMWE MEA development.

The electrode porosity is an important parameter for the well-functioning of the MEA (this will be discussed in the 7.2). Keeping in mind that spray coating inks usually have a lower solid content (2 ~ 3 wt. %) [90] than screen printing inks, the solvent evaporation and the final porous structure of the electrodes may differ and impact the cell performances. A hot pressing approach at high temperatures is highly dissuaded because of the poor thermal and

mechanical stability of the AEM. [93] Consequently, the MEA assembling is often proceeded by clamping the membrane in between both gas diffusion electrodes directly in the cell at room temperature.

However, Cho et al. [4] showed that 1 min hot pressing @ 50°C could improve the cell performances. Impedance measurements and IV curve cycling showed an increase of the high frequency resistance (HFR) with the pressing temperature, which was attributed to the Tokuyama membrane degradation. Without hot pressing a low frequency loop appeared which was ascribed to mass transport limitations. These limitations could be the result of a delamination of a part of the electrode. An analogous study was done by Park et al. [96]. Using Fumatech membrane, they found that hot pressing the CCS (70°C for 3 min at 0.1 MPa) resulted in higher performances of the MEA than without hot pressing. Still, MEAs produced by CCM method showed better performances than by CCS method. However, there are no aging tests reported in literature. The lower durability of CCM type MEAs might be a disadvantage compared to the CCS type.

In NEWELY, both approaches CCS and CCM will be investigated. It will contribute to a better understanding on the electrode integrity over load cycling when CCS is compared with CCM. In addition, different ink formulations will be tested, including high and low boiling point solvent and pore former additives, in order to develop the most efficient electrode microstructure.

7.2 Electrode preparation

At the electrode the electrochemical reactions take place. Survey on MEA fabrication gives some guidelines towards the preparation of the electrodes. The metal loadings reported in literature for the anode catalyst (noble metal IrO₂ or non-noble Ni, Fe, Cu based alloy) are high, ranging from 2 ~ 3 mg cm⁻². Also catalyst loadings of 40 mg cm⁻² of Ni-Mo have been reported [89]. The best result so far obtained with pure water were reported by Li et al. [97] with 1200 mA cm⁻² @ 2 V with 2,5 mg cm⁻² of IrO₂ and 2 mg cm⁻² of PtRu/C. It has to be highlighted that this research paper was focusing on the development of the ionomer and therefore most of the improvement was due to the ionomer development rather than the catalyst.

To the best of our knowledge, there are four commercially available ionomers: AS-4 from Tokuyama, FAA-3-SOLUT from Fumatech, AP1-HN8 from Ionomr and Sustainion from Dioxide materials. As a common feature of those compounds, they are very sensitive to high alkaline media (poor stability in high pH environment), so the adhesion strength of the catalyst layer with such ionomers could be weak [92]. A strategy for improving the adhesion consists in replacing the anion conductive polymer with a high adhesive polymer such as PTFE. Several papers have been reported for MEAs with PTFE as binder. Cho et. al [4] showed that the PTFE content in the electrode has a large impact on the cell performance. Low PTFE content does not allow a good adhesion strength of the electrode. Consequently, with time, the active layer delaminates, resulting in a decrease of performances. On the other hand, an excessive content of binder in the active layer leads to a coverage of the active layer and most probably a decrease of the electron conductivity in the electrode. The cumulative effect of both phenomena has shown to reduce the cell performance from 1.7 V

@ 200 mA cm⁻² with 12 wt. % of binder content to above 2.2 V at the same current density but with 20 wt. % of PTFE. Another approach described by Pushkareva [98] was using 5 wt% Nafion dispersion as ionomer. From our understanding, anion conductive ionomer shows poor adhesion properties, and PTFE binder is highly hydrophobic (may prevent the water to reach the active sites), therefore Nafion which is adhesive enough and also hydrophilic might be a promising alternative as binder. In this paper, different commercial membranes were tested with Nafion dispersion as binder. However, no durability tests were reported. Such disparity in the type of ionomer raises the question of the necessity of anion exchange ionomer in the electrode. Towards this question, Li et al. [97] have shown that an improved ionomer structure could considerably increase the AEMWE performance.

The electrode composition will be one of the most challenging aspects of the NEWELY project. A binder content in the range of 5 to 10 wt.% of PTFE or an anionic ionomer might be a good starting point. However, this value may change depending on the membrane and the catalyst loadings. Based on the recommendations of the WP2 partners, different approaches of binder will be evaluated. In addition, a spray of anionic binder after sintering of the PTFE based electrode could be considered in order to obtain both, high anionic conductivity and high adhesion strength. Lastly, binder free electrode developed by DLR will be tested since it has been demonstrated to show interesting result in terms of performance (2 V @ 2500 mA cm⁻² 65 °C with 1 M KOH) [99]. However, those developments were performed in KOH feeding solution and consequently additional tests with pure water need to be validated in the project.

7.3 Solution in NEWELY

Many papers [7, 100, 101] dealing with AEMWE show that an increase in KOH concentration leads to better performances, mostly due to a better OH⁻ conductivity. However, because of the low chemical stability of the membrane, cells with high pH solution should be avoided [92]. As shown by Ito et al., K₂CO₃ additives contribute to improve the cell performances better than KOH does. The authors suggest that a larger OH⁻ concentration in the electrode with K₂CO₃ than with KOH was the cause of the better performances with the carbonate additives.

The main objective of the NEWELY project is to run the cell with pure water. The best results up to now in such conditions were published by Ayers [102] with 1,9 V @ 500 mA cm⁻² (the temperature is not mentioned) and Li et al [97] who reported 1,9 V @ 1000 mA cm⁻² and 85 °C. Again, they developed improved membrane and ionomer to achieve such a result.

7.4 MEA requirements and targets in NEWELY

To previously define the properties for the final MEA of the project is hardly possible, since designing and optimizing an electrode and MEA towards the best performance is a complex task where the interactions of several parameters play a crucial role. The material loading should be kept as low as possible, especially with PGM material, to keep the production costs low. However, with less active, non PGM catalyst material often a high loading is

necessary to reach a sufficient performance of the cell. The ratio of the electrocatalyst and the supporting material, but also the ionomer or binder is a crucial factor for the performance. A higher amount of support material usually results in an increased pore volume and thus in mass transport gains. However, kinetic losses can occur due to an inaccessible catalyst. Also, the choice and the amount of the solvent for the catalyst ink as well as the conditions during the coating and drying process play an important role for the electrode design and therefore for the performance of the MEA. Regarding the AEM, thin membranes lead to an improved OH- conductivity. However, with thinner membranes problems can occur regarding the mechanical stability and the gas permeation. For the performance of the MEA in Milestone M3.3 of the NEWELY project the target value of 2 V @ 1 A cm⁻² was defined. Based on this literature survey on MEAs for AEMWE, in Table 6 we gather the main specifications of each element for an efficient MEA and the strategies that will be adopted within the NEWELY project.

Components	Requirements	State of the art	NEWELY approach
OER catalyst	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high catalytic activity at neutral pH (<470 mV overpotential @ 1 mA cm⁻² [103]) - good chemical stability - non noble catalyst 	Nickel based alloy above 3 mg cm ⁻²	Ni and Fe based oxides on different functional supports
HER catalyst	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high catalytic activity at neutral pH (<100 mV overpotential @ 10 mA cm⁻² [104]) - good chemical stability - non noble catalyst 	Nickel or Copper based alloys above 3 mg cm ⁻²	Mo ₂ C or related on different functional supports
Binder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - good chemical stability - high anionic conductivity (high IEC based on membrane chemistry) - high adhesion strength 	PTFE 5-10 wt.% of the electrode	membrane chemistry PTFE free PTFE
Membrane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high OH⁻ conductivity (> 50 mS cm⁻¹) - good chemical stability - low gas permeation 	hydrocarbon backbone with trimethylamine functional group	Styrene-olefine copolymer as backbone and trimethylamine free membrane
MEA type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - long term stability - high anionic transport at interface electrode/membrane - low chemical and mechanical membrane degradation 	CCS no heating / pressure during MEA fabrication	CSS and CCM will be investigated
GDL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high chemical stability - high electron conductivity - high water diffusion - high gas diffusion - low cost 	Nickel foam (anode) Carbon paper (cathode)	Nickel and Stainless steel various combination of the PTFE treatment and modification of the MPL layer
Solution feeding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high electron conductivity - does not carbonate 	KOH (0.1 to 1 mol dm ⁻³) anode and cathode compartment	pure water on both electrodes

Table 6 Main specifications of the components comprising an AEM WE, adopted from [103, 104]

8 Conclusion

Catalysts of the anodic oxygen and cathodic hydrogen evolution reactions represent important parts of the NEWELY developed cell, as they allow meeting project targets in the produced cell/stack efficiency. Important aspects represent in this respect following points:

- they will be based on non-critical raw materials;
- they will be stable under conditions of alkaline membrane water electrolysis with demineralised water used as a circulating medium.

The present deliverable summarises information available in the literature on the catalysts tested for this particular process and for demineralised water conditions. On the base of available information, Ni and Fe based materials were evaluated as the promising choice for OER reaction in neutral to alkaline solutions. For HER, carbides of the 3d-transition metals were identified as interesting materials. As benchmark materials Mo_2C and $\text{Ni}_x\text{Fe}_y\text{O}_z$ were selected for HER and OER respectively. Both these materials are produced by NEWELY consortium member CENmat.

Adequate attention is paid also to remaining parts of the electrodes and MEA. It concerns especially LGDL/GDL. As an alternative to Ti used in PEM water electrolysis stainless steel and potentially Ni are proposed. All the information available is then summarised in proposed approaches to the MEA production. Finally, requirements put on the individual components, as well as on MEA are summarised. Thus, it can be concluded, that this deliverable represents a good base for activities developed within NEWELY project WP3 entitled *Catalyst, MPL and MEA specifications and requirements*.

9 Literature

- [1] Chanda D, Hnát J, Bystron T, Paidar M, Bouzek K. Optimization of synthesis of the nickel-cobalt oxide based anode electrocatalyst and of the related membrane-electrode assembly for alkaline water electrolysis. *Journal of Power Sources*. 2017;347:247-58.
- [2] Wang J, Yue X, Yang Y, Sirisomboonchai S, Wang P, Ma X, et al. Earth-abundant transition-metal-based bifunctional catalysts for overall electrochemical water splitting: A review. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*. 2020;819:153346-69.
- [3] Anantharaj S, Aravindan V. Developments and Perspectives in 3d Transition-Metal-Based Electrocatalysts for Neutral and Near-Neutral Water Electrolysis. *Adv Energy Mater*. 2020;10:1902666-96.
- [4] Cho MK, Park HY, Choe S, Yoo SJ, Kim JY, Kim HJ, et al. Factors in electrode fabrication for performance enhancement of anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. *Journal of Power Sources*. 2017;347:283-90.
- [5] Lim A, Kim HJ, Henkensmeier D, Jong Yoo S, Young Kim J, Young Lee S, et al. A study on electrode fabrication and operation variables affecting the performance of anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*. 2019;76:410-8.
- [6] Cho MK, Park H-Y, Lee HJ, Kim H-J, Lim A, Henkensmeier D, et al. Alkaline anion exchange membrane water electrolysis: Effects of electrolyte feed method and electrode binder content. *Journal of Power Sources*. 2018;382:22-9.
- [7] Su X, Gao L, Hu L, Qaisrani NA, Yan X, Zhang W, et al. Novel piperidinium functionalized anionic membrane for alkaline polymer electrolysis with excellent electrochemical properties. *Journal of Membrane Science*. 2019:283-92.
- [8] Wang X, Zheng Y, Sheng W, Xu ZJ, Jaroniec M, Qiao S-Z. Strategies for design of electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution under alkaline conditions. *Materials Today*. 2020.
- [9] Schmidt TJ, Ross PN, Markovic NM. Temperature dependent surface electrochemistry on Pt single crystals in alkaline electrolytes: Part 2. The hydrogen evolution/oxidation reaction. *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry*. 2002;524-525:252-60.
- [10] Marković NM, Schmidt TJ, Grgur BN, Gasteiger HA, Behm RJ, Ross PN. Effect of Temperature on Surface Processes at the Pt(111)-Liquid Interface: Hydrogen Adsorption, Oxide Formation, and CO Oxidation. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*. 1999;103:8568-77.
- [11] Anantharaj S, Ede SR, Sakthikumar K, Karthick K, Mishra S, Kundu S. Recent Trends and Perspectives in Electrochemical Water Splitting with an Emphasis on Sulfide, Selenide, and Phosphide Catalysts of Fe, Co, and Ni: A Review. *ACS Catalysis*. 2016;6:8069-97.
- [12] Nikiforov A. New Construction and Catalyst Support Materials for Water Electrolysis at Elevated Temperatures 2011.

- [13] Zhang R, Wang X, Yu S, Wen T, Zhu X, Yang F, et al. Ternary NiCo₂P_x Nanowires as pH-Universal Electrocatalysts for Highly Efficient Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Advanced Materials*. 2017;29:1605502.
- [14] Zhang B, Lui YH, Ni H, Hu S. Bimetallic (Fe_xNi_{1-x})₂P nanoarrays as exceptionally efficient electrocatalysts for oxygen evolution in alkaline and neutral media. *Nano Energy*. 2017;38:553-60.
- [15] Liu B, Zhang L, Xiong W, Ma M. Cobalt-Nanocrystal-Assembled Hollow Nanoparticles for Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Generation from Neutral-pH Water. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2016;55:6725-9.
- [16] Tian J, Liu Q, Asiri AM, Sun X. Self-Supported Nanoporous Cobalt Phosphide Nanowire Arrays: An Efficient 3D Hydrogen-Evolving Cathode over the Wide Range of pH 0–14. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2014;136:7587-90.
- [17] You B, Liu X, Hu G, Gul S, Yano J, Jiang D-e, et al. Universal Surface Engineering of Transition Metals for Superior Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution in Neutral Water. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2017;139:12283-90.
- [18] Callejas JF, McEnaney JM, Read CG, Crompton JC, Biacchi AJ, Popczun EJ, et al. Electrocatalytic and Photocatalytic Hydrogen Production from Acidic and Neutral-pH Aqueous Solutions Using Iron Phosphide Nanoparticles. *ACS Nano*. 2014;8:11101-7.
- [19] Feng L-L, Li G-D, Liu Y, Wu Y, Chen H, Wang Y, et al. Carbon-Armored Co₉S₈ Nanoparticles as All-pH Efficient and Durable H₂-Evolving Electrocatalysts. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 2015;7:980-8.
- [20] Jin S. Are Metal Chalcogenides, Nitrides, and Phosphides Oxygen Evolution Catalysts or Bifunctional Catalysts? *ACS Energy Letters*. 2017;2:1937-8.
- [21] Tang C, Pu Z, Liu Q, Asiri AM, Sun X. NiS₂ nanosheets array grown on carbon cloth as an efficient 3D hydrogen evolution cathode. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2015;153:508-14.
- [22] Fan M, Gao R, Zou Y-C, Wang D, Bai N, Li G-D, et al. An efficient nanostructured copper(I) sulfide-based hydrogen evolution electrocatalyst at neutral pH. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2016;215:366-73.
- [23] Anantharaj S, Kennedy J, Kundu S. Microwave-Initiated Facile Formation of Ni₃Se₄ Nanoassemblies for Enhanced and Stable Water Splitting in Neutral and Alkaline Media. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 2017;9:8714-28.
- [24] Peng Z, Jia D, Al-Enizi AM, Elzatahry AA, Zheng G. From Water Oxidation to Reduction: Homologous Ni–Co Based Nanowires as Complementary Water Splitting Electrocatalysts. *Adv Energy Mater*. 2015;5:1402031.
- [25] Sun Y, Bigi JP, Piro NA, Tang ML, Long JR, Chang CJ. Molecular Cobalt Pentapyridine Catalysts for Generating Hydrogen from Water. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2011;133:9212-5.

- [26] Kleingardner JG, Kandemir B, Bren KL. Hydrogen Evolution from Neutral Water under Aerobic Conditions Catalyzed by Cobalt Microperoxidase-11. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2014;136:4-7.
- [27] Su X-J, Gao M, Jiao L, Liao R-Z, Siegbahn PEM, Cheng J-P, et al. Electrocatalytic Water Oxidation by a Dinuclear Copper Complex in a Neutral Aqueous Solution. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2015;54:4909-14.
- [28] Garcia-Esparza AT, Cha D, Ou Y, Kubota J, Domen K, Takanebe K. Tungsten Carbide Nanoparticles as Efficient Cocatalysts for Photocatalytic Overall Water Splitting. *ChemSusChem*. 2013;6:168-81.
- [29] Fan C. Study of Electrodeposited Nickel-Molybdenum, Nickel-Tungsten, Cobalt-Molybdenum, and Cobalt-Tungsten as Hydrogen Electrodes in Alkaline Water Electrolysis. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*. 1994;141:382.
- [30] Wang Y, Zhang G, Xu W, Wan P, Lu Z, Li Y, et al. A 3D Nanoporous Ni–Mo Electrocatalyst with Negligible Overpotential for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution. *ChemElectroChem*. 2014;1:1138-44.
- [31] Li Y, Wang H, Xie L, Liang Y, Hong G, Dai H. MoS₂ Nanoparticles Grown on Graphene: An Advanced Catalyst for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2011;133:7296-9.
- [32] Faber MS, Dziedzic R, Lukowski MA, Kaiser NS, Ding Q, Jin S. High-Performance Electrocatalysis Using Metallic Cobalt Pyrite (CoS₂) Micro- and Nanostructures. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2014;136:10053-61.
- [33] Tran PD, Chiam SY, Boix PP, Ren Y, Pramana SS, Fize J, et al. Novel cobalt/nickel–tungsten-sulfide catalysts for electrocatalytic hydrogen generation from water. *Energy & Environmental Science*. 2013;6:2452-9.
- [34] Voiry D, Yamaguchi H, Li J, Silva R, Alves DCB, Fujita T, et al. Enhanced catalytic activity in strained chemically exfoliated WS₂ nanosheets for hydrogen evolution. *Nat Mater*. 2013;12:850-5.
- [35] Xu Y-F, Gao M-R, Zheng Y-R, Jiang J, Yu S-H. Nickel/Nickel(II) Oxide Nanoparticles Anchored onto Cobalt(IV) Diselenide Nanobelts for the Electrochemical Production of Hydrogen. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2013;52:8546-50.
- [36] Kiran V, Mukherjee D, Jenjeti RN, Sampath S. Active guests in the MoS₂/MoSe₂ host lattice: efficient hydrogen evolution using few-layer alloys of MoS₂(1-x)Se_{2x}. *Nanoscale*. 2014;6:12856-63.
- [37] Zhou H, Wang Y, He R, Yu F, Sun J, Wang F, et al. One-step synthesis of self-supported porous NiSe₂/Ni hybrid foam: An efficient 3D electrode for hydrogen evolution reaction. *Nano Energy*. 2016;20:29-36.
- [38] Popczun EJ, McKone JR, Read CG, Biacchi AJ, Wiltrout AM, Lewis NS, et al. Nanostructured Nickel Phosphide as an Electrocatalyst for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2013;135:9267-70.

- [39] Popczun EJ, Read CG, Roske CW, Lewis NS, Schaak RE. Highly Active Electrocatalysis of the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction by Cobalt Phosphide Nanoparticles. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2014;53:5427-30.
- [40] Jiang P, Liu Q, Liang Y, Tian J, Asiri AM, Sun X. A Cost-Effective 3D Hydrogen Evolution Cathode with High Catalytic Activity: FeP Nanowire Array as the Active Phase. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2014;53:12855-9.
- [41] Kibsgaard J, Jaramillo TF. Molybdenum Phosphosulfide: An Active, Acid-Stable, Earth-Abundant Catalyst for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2014;53:14433-7.
- [42] Liang H-W, Brüller S, Dong R, Zhang J, Feng X, Müllen K. Molecular metal–Nx centres in porous carbon for electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution. *Nature Communications*. 2015;6:7992.
- [43] Chen W-F, Sasaki K, Ma C, Frenkel AI, Marinkovic N, Muckerman JT, et al. Hydrogen-Evolution Catalysts Based on Non-Noble Metal Nickel–Molybdenum Nitride Nanosheets. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2012;51:6131-5.
- [44] Cao B, Veith GM, Neufeind JC, Adzic RR, Khalifah PG. Mixed Close-Packed Cobalt Molybdenum Nitrides as Non-noble Metal Electrocatalysts for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2013;135:19186-92.
- [45] Vrabel H, Hu X. Molybdenum Boride and Carbide Catalyze Hydrogen Evolution in both Acidic and Basic Solutions. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2012;51:12703-6.
- [46] Liao L, Wang S, Xiao J, Bian X, Zhang Y, Scanlon MD, et al. A nanoporous molybdenum carbide nanowire as an electrocatalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction. *Energy & Environmental Science*. 2014;7:387-92.
- [47] Shi Z, Wang Y, Lin H, Zhang H, Shen M, Xie S, et al. Porous nanoMoC@graphite shell derived from a MOFs-directed strategy: an efficient electrocatalyst for the hydrogen evolution reaction. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2016;4:6006-13.
- [48] Fan L, Liu PF, Yan X, Gu L, Yang ZZ, Yang HG, et al. Atomically isolated nickel species anchored on graphitized carbon for efficient hydrogen evolution electrocatalysis. *Nature Communications*. 2016;7:10667.
- [49] Lu Q, Hutchings GS, Yu W, Zhou Y, Forest RV, Tao R, et al. Highly porous non-precious bimetallic electrocatalysts for efficient hydrogen evolution. *Nature Communications*. 2015;6:6567.
- [50] Roger I, Shipman MA, Symes MD. Earth-abundant catalysts for electrochemical and photoelectrochemical water splitting. *Nat Rev Chem*. 2017;1:0003.
- [51] Yan Y, Xia BY, Zhao B, Wang X. A review on noble-metal-free bifunctional heterogeneous catalysts for overall electrochemical water splitting. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2016;4:17587-603.
- [52] Tahir M, Pan L, Idrees F, Zhang X, Wang L, Zou J-J, et al. Electrocatalytic oxygen evolution reaction for energy conversion and storage: A comprehensive review. *Nano Energy*. 2017;37:136-57.

- [53] He J, Peng Y, Sun Z, Cheng W, Liu Q, Feng Y, et al. Realizing High Water Splitting Activity on Co₃O₄ Nanowire Arrays under Neutral Environment. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2014;119:64-71.
- [54] Zhang Y, Cui B, Qin Z, Lin H, Li J. Hierarchical wreath-like Au–Co(OH)₂ microclusters for water oxidation at neutral pH. *Nanoscale*. 2013;5:6826-33.
- [55] Lin H, Zhang Y, Wang G, Li J-B. Cobalt-based layered double hydroxides as oxygen evolving electrocatalysts in neutral electrolyte. *Frontiers of Materials Science*. 2012;6:142-8.
- [56] Cai P, Huang J, Chen J, Wen Z. Oxygen-Containing Amorphous Cobalt Sulfide Porous Nanocubes as High-Activity Electrocatalysts for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction in an Alkaline/Neutral Medium. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2017;56:4858-61.
- [57] Esswein AJ, Surendranath Y, Reece SY, Nocera DG. Highly active cobalt phosphate and borate based oxygen evolving catalysts operating in neutral and natural waters. *Energy & Environmental Science*. 2011;4:499-504.
- [58] Xie F, Wu H, Mou J, Lin D, Xu C, Wu C, et al. Ni₃N@Ni-Ci nanoarray as a highly active and durable non-noble-metal electrocatalyst for water oxidation at near-neutral pH. *Journal of Catalysis*. 2017;356:165-72.
- [59] Fabbri E, Haberer A, Waltar K, Kötz R, Schmidt TJ. Developments and perspectives of oxide-based catalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction. *Catalysis Science & Technology*. 2014;4:3800-21.
- [60] Frydendal R, Paoli EA, Knudsen BP, Wickman B, Malacrida P, Stephens IEL, et al. Benchmarking the Stability of Oxygen Evolution Reaction Catalysts: The Importance of Monitoring Mass Losses. *ChemElectroChem*. 2014;1:2075-81.
- [61] Meng Y, Song W, Huang H, Ren Z, Chen S-Y, Suib SL. Structure–Property Relationship of Bifunctional MnO₂ Nanostructures: Highly Efficient, Ultra-Stable Electrochemical Water Oxidation and Oxygen Reduction Reaction Catalysts Identified in Alkaline Media. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2014;136:11452-64.
- [62] Chen M, Wu Y, Han Y, Lin X, Sun J, Zhang W, et al. An Iron-based Film for Highly Efficient Electrocatalytic Oxygen Evolution from Neutral Aqueous Solution. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces*. 2015;7:21852-9.
- [63] Wang J, Zuo S, Wei G, Niu Y, Guo L, Chen Z. Investigation of Fe-Based Integrated Electrodes for Water Oxidation in Neutral and Alkaline Solutions. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 2019;123:12313-20.
- [64] Li P, Jin Z, Xiao D. A one-step synthesis of Co–P–B/rGO at room temperature with synergistically enhanced electrocatalytic activity in neutral solution. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2014;2:18420-7.
- [65] Ahn HS, Tilley TD. Electrocatalytic Water Oxidation at Neutral pH by a Nanostructured Co(PO₃)₂ Anode. *Advanced Functional Materials*. 2013;23:227-33.
- [66] Zhao Y, Chen S, Sun B, Su D, Huang X, Liu H, et al. Graphene-Co₃O₄ nanocomposite as electrocatalyst with high performance for oxygen evolution reaction. *Sci Rep*. 2015;5:7629.

[67] Merrill MD, Dougherty RC. Metal Oxide Catalysts for the Evolution of O₂ from H₂O. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 2008;112:3655-66.

[68] Lu X, Zhao C. Electrodeposition of hierarchically structured three-dimensional nickel–iron electrodes for efficient oxygen evolution at high current densities. *Nature Communications*. 2015;6:6616.

[69] Gong M, Li Y, Wang H, Liang Y, Wu JZ, Zhou J, et al. An Advanced Ni–Fe Layered Double Hydroxide Electrocatalyst for Water Oxidation. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2013;135:8452-5.

[70] Lambert TN, Vigil JA, White SE, Davis DJ, Limmer SJ, Burton PD, et al. Electrodeposited Ni_xCo_{3-x}O₄ nanostructured films as bifunctional oxygen electrocatalysts. *Chemical Communications*. 2015;51:9511-4.

[71] Tian J, Cheng N, Liu Q, Sun X, He Y, Asiri AM. Self-supported NiMo hollow nanorod array: an efficient 3D bifunctional catalytic electrode for overall water splitting. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2015;3:20056-9.

[72] Zhang B, Zheng X, Voznyy O, Comin R, Bajdich M, García-Melchor M, et al. Homogeneously dispersed multimetal oxygen-evolving catalysts. *Science*. 2016;352:333-7.

[73] Suntivich J, May KJ, Gasteiger HA, Goodenough JB, Shao-Horn Y. A Perovskite Oxide Optimized for Oxygen Evolution Catalysis from Molecular Orbital Principles. *Science*. 2011;334:1383-5.

[74] Haber JA, Cai Y, Jung S, Xiang C, Mitrovic S, Jin J, et al. Discovering Ce-rich oxygen evolution catalysts, from high throughput screening to water electrolysis. *Energy & Environmental Science*. 2014;7:682-8.

[75] Smith RDL, Prévot MS, Fagan RD, Zhang Z, Sedach PA, Siu MKJ, et al. Photochemical Route for Accessing Amorphous Metal Oxide Materials for Water Oxidation Catalysis. *Science*. 2013;340:60-3.

[76] Kanan MW, Nocera DG. In Situ Formation of an Oxygen-Evolving Catalyst in Neutral Water Containing Phosphate and Co²⁺. *Science*. 2008;321:1072-5.

[77] Surendranath Y, Dincă M, Nocera DG. Electrolyte-Dependent Electrosynthesis and Activity of Cobalt-Based Water Oxidation Catalysts. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2009;131:2615-20.

[78] Koza JA, He Z, Miller AS, Switzer JA. Electrodeposition of Crystalline Co₃O₄—A Catalyst for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction. *Chemistry of Materials*. 2012;24:3567-73.

[79] Gerken JB, Landis EC, Hamers RJ, Stahl SS. Fluoride-Modulated Cobalt Catalysts for Electrochemical Oxidation of Water under Non-Alkaline Conditions. *ChemSusChem*. 2010;3:1176-9.

[80] Jiang N, You B, Sheng M, Sun Y. Electrodeposited Cobalt-Phosphorous-Derived Films as Competent Bifunctional Catalysts for Overall Water Splitting. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2015;54:6251-4.

- [81] Li D, Baydoun H, Verani CN, Brock SL. Efficient Water Oxidation Using CoMnP Nanoparticles. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2016;138:4006-9.
- [82] Bediako DK, Surendranath Y, Nocera DG. Mechanistic Studies of the Oxygen Evolution Reaction Mediated by a Nickel–Borate Thin Film Electrocatalyst. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2013;135:3662-74.
- [83] Zhao Y, Jia X, Chen G, Shang L, Waterhouse GIN, Wu L-Z, et al. Ultrafine NiO Nanosheets Stabilized by TiO₂ from Monolayer NiTi-LDH Precursors: An Active Water Oxidation Electrocatalyst. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2016;138:6517-24.
- [84] Ramírez A, Hillebrand P, Stellmach D, May MM, Bogdanoff P, Fiechter S. Evaluation of MnOx, Mn₂O₃, and Mn₃O₄ Electrodeposited Films for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction of Water. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 2014;118:14073-81.
- [85] Liu G, Bai H, Ji Y, Wang L, Wen Y, Lin H, et al. A highly efficient alkaline HER Co–Mo bimetallic carbide catalyst with an optimized Mo d-orbital electronic state. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2019;7:12434-9.
- [86] Mo J, Kang Z, Yang G, Retterer ST, Cullen DA, Toops TJ, et al. Thin liquid/gas diffusion layers for high-efficiency hydrogen production from water splitting. *Applied Energy*. 2016;177:817-22.
- [87] Lettenmeier P, Kolb S, Sata N, Fallisch A, Zielke L, Thiele S, et al. Comprehensive investigation of novel pore-graded gas diffusion layers for high-performance and cost-effective proton exchange membrane electrolyzers. *Energy & Environmental Science*. 2017;10:2521-33.
- [88] Li Y, Kang Z, Deng X, Yang G, Yu S, Mo J, et al. Wettability effects of thin titanium liquid/gas diffusion layers in proton exchange membrane electrolyzer cells. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2019;298:704-8.
- [89] Vincent I, Bessarabov D. Low cost hydrogen production by anion exchange membrane electrolysis: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 2018;81:1690-704.
- [90] Fortin P, Khoza T, Cao X, Martinsen SY, Oyarce Barnett A, Holdcroft S. High-performance alkaline water electrolysis using Aemion™ anion exchange membranes. *Journal of Power Sources*. 2020;451:227814.
- [91] Schalenbach M, Tjarks G, Carmo M, Lueke W, Mueller M, Stolten D. Acidic or Alkaline? Towards a New Perspective on the Efficiency of Water Electrolysis. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*. 2016;163:F3197-F208.
- [92] Ito H, Kawaguchi N, Someya S, Munakata T, Miyazaki N, Ishida M, et al. Experimental investigation of electrolytic solution for anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 2018;43:17030-9.
- [93] Carbone A, Zignani SC, Gatto I, Trocino S, Aricò AS. Assessment of the FAA3-50 polymer electrolyte in combination with a NiMn₂O₄ anode catalyst for anion exchange membrane water electrolysis. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 2020;45:9285-92.
- [94] Suzuki S, Muroyama H, Matsui T, Eguchi K. Influence of CO₂ dissolution into anion exchange membrane on fuel cell performance. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2013;88:552-8.

- [95] Parrondo J, Arges CG, Niedzwiecki M, Anderson EB, Ayers KE, Ramani V. Degradation of anion exchange membranes used for hydrogen production by ultrapure water electrolysis. *Rsc Advances*. 2014;4:9875-9.
- [96] Park JE, Kang SY, Oh SH, Kim JK, Lim MS, Ahn CY, et al. High-performance anion-exchange membrane water electrolysis. *Electrochimica Acta*. 2019;295:99-106.
- [97] Li D, Park EJ, Zhu W, Shi Q, Zhou Y, Tian H, et al. Highly quaternized polystyrene ionomers for high performance anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers. *Nature Energy*. 2020.
- [98] Pushkareva IV, Pushkarev AS, Grigoriev SA, Modisha P, Bessarabov DG. Comparative study of anion exchange membranes for low-cost water electrolysis. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 2019.
- [99] Razmjooei F, Reißner R, Gago AS, Ansar A. Highly Active Binder Free Plasma Sprayed Non-Noble Metal Electrodes for Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolysis at Different Reduced KOH Concentrations. *ECS Transactions*. 2019;92:689-702.
- [100] Hnát J, Plevova M, Tufa RA, Zitka J, Paidar M, Bouzek K. Development and testing of a novel catalyst-coated membrane with platinum-free catalysts for alkaline water electrolysis. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 2019;44:17493-504.
- [101] Hnát J, Kodým R, Denk K, Paidar M, Žitka J, Bouzek K. Design of a Zero-Gap Laboratory-Scale Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Alkaline Water Electrolysis Stack. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*. 2019;91:821-32.
- [102] Ayers KE, Anderson EB, Capuano CB, Niedzwiecki M, Hickner MA, Wang CY, et al. Characterization of Anion Exchange Membrane Technology for Low Cost Electrolysis. *ECS Transactions*. 2013;45:121-30.
- [103] Surendranath Y, Kanan MW, Nocera DG. Mechanistic Studies of the Oxygen Evolution Reaction by a Cobalt-Phosphate Catalyst at Neutral pH. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 2010;132:16501-9.
- [104] Abdullah MI, Hameed A, Zhang N, Ma M. Nickel Nanocrystal Assemblies as Efficient Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Evolution from pH-Neutral Aqueous Solution. *ChemElectroChem*. 2019;6:2100-6.